

BRILLO: Personalised Behaviours for a Long-term HRI

Alessandra Rossi¹ and Silvia Rossi¹

Abstract—The BRILLO (Bartending Robot for Interactive Long-Lasting Operations) project’s goal is to create an autonomous and endearing robotic bartender that is able to naturally interact with its customers while preparing their drinks. To this extent, we developed a three-layer ROS architecture integrating perception, decision-making and execution layers for controlling the behaviours of the robot and handling personalised multi-party interactions with people. The BRILLO robot bartender provides personalised service and interactions, and recommendations based on users’ preferences for drinks and interaction styles.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human bartenders do not only provide a service, but they ensure customer retention by creating a long-lasting relationship. Indeed, one of the main challenges in food and beverage robotic industry is connected to the loss of interest in the technology (i.e., a robot) if this does not meet people’s expectations of the service and, most importantly, their social expectations of the robot. For this reason, customers’ satisfaction is strongly connected to the social skills of a service robot. Following such a scenario, the project BRILLO aims to deploy a robot that is able to model its behaviours in rich and multi-modal interactions in real commercial activities [1]. The development of the BRILLO bartender robot includes natural communication modes (verbal and non-verbal), recommendations and personalised interactions to ensure the users’ engagement with the robot. In this paper, we provide an overview of BRILLO’s architecture, its ability to personalise and recommend both interaction and drinks, its ability to manage natural interactions, and we show people’s initial considerations and perceptions of the robot.

II. THE SCENARIO

In our scenario, people start to use BRILLO services by being welcomed - in case they are returning customers - and register - in case it is their first visit - by a totem kiosk. At the kiosk, customers place their orders, and then they can move to the counter where the BRILLO robot bartender recognises them via biometric facial recognition, and after confirming or changing their order, starts the interaction. The BRILLO bartender robot is in charge of preparing and serving drinks (cocktails and smoothies) at the counter, while

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¹A. Rossi and S. Rossi are with the Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Technologies - DIETI, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, Italy {alessandra.rossi, silvia.rossi}@unina.it

Fig. 1: The BRILLO robots.

entertaining the customers with light conversations about real and humorous news. The BRILLO robot can prepare drinks for only two customers at a time. For this reason, we decided to have the robot interact with just these two customers, and only acknowledge new customers by greeting them. The robot moves to serve and interacts with new customers only when it ends the previous orders.

III. THE BRILLO ROBOT

The BRILLO robot is composed of two Kuka¹ LBR iiwa 14 R820 robotic arms (each of 7 DoF and gripper) attached to a fixed-torso for manipulating the drinks and their ingredients, and a Furhat Robotics head² (called Furhat, 3 DoF) for naturally interacting with the users (see Figure 1). The robot’s functionalities are enhanced by the external support of a 4x2MP IR 180° Multi-sensor Panoramic Network Bullet camera³ and two microphone arrays⁴ on the right and on the left of the robot.

IV. THE BRILLO ARCHITECTURE

Our system is based on a three-layer control architecture that follows a user-centred approach. The architecture allows for modelling both reactivity and pro-activity in the robot behaviours, and interaction with multi-users by means of multiple instantiated intentions, while modelling long-term knowledge as well as situational assessment through beliefs update mechanisms. The architecture is composed of: 1) a Percepts layer that handles the users’ detection, facial biometric recognition, and the presence of a group of users; 2) a Context-awareness layer that builds the agents and

¹Kuka Robotics <https://www.kuka.com>

²Furhat Robotics <https://furhatrobotics.com>

³<https://us.dahuasecurity.com/?product=4x2mp-ir-180-multi-sensor-panoramic-network-bullet>

⁴PureAudio USB Array Microphone

situational awareness based on the information related to the users' orders, preferences, social engagement with their group and the robot, and emotions; and 3) an Execution layer that plans the robot's actions for preparing drinks and interacting with the users according to the built beliefs and perceptions from the previous two layers.

V. THE PERSONALISATION OF THE HRI

The personalization and recommendation of the interaction with BRILLO take place via several modalities. From the hardware, the Furhat head reproduces facial movements, emotions, and gestures, while the Kuka arms are used for the preparation of the drinks and imitating the typical humans' gestures used by humans when they are engaging in human-human interactions. For the software, BRILLO personalization begins with customers' recognition, identification of their persona, interests, and building their preferences and needs by using data from new and previous interactions.

A. Animacy and anthropomorphism

Social interactions are observer-dependent, and the appearance of the robot affects people's initial considerations and impressions, as a consequence it can have a significant impact on the quality of the human-robot interaction. In particular, the anthropomorphic design of the robot may facilitate the initialisation of social interaction but also increase possible bias based on the gender and features of the BRILLO robot [2]. We also observed that other human characteristics, such as roles, personality, and serving styles may affect people's positive perception of BRILLO ([3], [4]).

While increasing the anthropomorphic resemblance and social presence of robots, people's expectations of these robots also increase. For this reason, it is very important that the BRILLO robot is able to recognise, understand and reproduce human social cues. In particular, we focused on the generation of different and realistic facial expressions that can be appropriate and responsive to the contextualised human-robot interaction (HRI). Our efforts have been focused on developing mechanisms for the generation of emotional facial expressions ([5], [6]).

B. Privacy concerns

Personalised experiences with service robots positively affect people's perception of the robot, but it also raises concerns related to the need to share people's personal information with the robot. However, we believe that people might respond to a disclosure of information by a robot as they would do with human bartenders in real scenarios [7].

C. Trust, engagement and error interaction recovery

Since robots' hardware and software may have limitations and, as a consequence, fail their tasks or produce erroneous behaviours, it is very important to keep customers' engagement and attention towards the robot [8], and identify the appropriate methods to recover from an error, and foster people's trust in the robot in HRI. Some of the mechanisms tested within the BRILLO project include the use of humour and sarcasm [9], and Theory of Mind [10].

VI. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

We tested our system during an Italian faire called Maker Faire, and we collected the perceptions of 63 people regarding the robot's performance and interactions. In particular, we asked participants to evaluate BRILLO's attractiveness, learnability, efficiency, dependability, stimulation, and originality. Overall, participants rated very favourably BRILLO for attractiveness, ease of use and understanding, and originality. However, the robot was considered less efficient and trustworthy than expected, even if their ratings were not negative. We believe that our test-case was limited because participants were not able to really drink the beverages due to the regulations of the faire.

VII. FUTURE WORKS

The first prototype of the BRILLO robot that is able of preparing and serving drinks while engaging human customers in conversations has been developed and tested in the wild. However, a fundamental future step is to integrate BRILLO in a real commercial activity for longer exposure with human, and to further investigate how to create a long-lasting relationship for ensuring customer retention.

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